

On the F.Smarandache LCM function and its mean value

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. The main purpose of this paper is to use the elementary methods to study the mean value of the F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords F.Smarandache LCM function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. For example, the first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1$, $SL(2) = 2$, $SL(3) = 3$, $SL(4) = 4$, $SL(5) = 5$, $SL(6) = 3$, $SL(7) = 7$, $SL(8) = 8$, $SL(9) = 9$, $SL(10) = 5$, $SL(11) = 11$, $SL(12) = 4$, $SL(13) = 13$, $SL(14) = 7$, $SL(15) = 5, \dots$. About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, some authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see reference [3] and [4]. For example, Murthy [3] showed that if n is a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $S(n)$ denotes the Smarandache function, i.e., $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, m \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Simultaneously, Murthy [3] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n ? \quad (1)$$

Le Maohua [4] completely solved this problem, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}, i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

The main purpose of this paper is to use the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $SL(n)$, and obtain a sharper asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. Let $k \geq 2$ be a fixed integer. Then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

From our Theorem we may immediately deduce the following:

Corollary. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall prove our theorem directly. In fact for any positive integer $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n , then from [3] we know that

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_s^{\alpha_s}\}. \quad (2)$$

Now we consider the summation

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \sum_{n \in A} SL(n) + \sum_{n \in B} SL(n), \quad (3)$$

where we have divided the interval $[1, x]$ into two sets A and B . A denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that there exists a prime p with $p|n$ and $p > \sqrt{n}$. And B denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ with $n \notin A$. From (2) and the definition of A we have

$$\sum_{n \in A} SL(n) = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p|n, \sqrt{n} < p}} SL(n) = \sum_{\substack{pn \leq x \\ n < p}} SL(pn) = \sum_{\substack{pn \leq x \\ n < p}} p = \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p. \quad (4)$$

By Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [5]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [6]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p &= \frac{x}{n} \cdot \pi\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) - n \cdot \pi(n) - \int_n^{\frac{x}{n}} \pi(y) dy \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2n^2 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^2 \cdot \ln^i n}{n^2 \cdot \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{n^2 \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where we have used the estimate $n \leq \sqrt{x}$, and all b_i are computable constants.

Note that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^i n}{n^2}$ is convergent for all $i = 2, 3, \dots, k$. From (4) and (5) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in A} SL(n) &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x^2}{2n^2 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^2 \cdot \ln^i n}{n^2 \cdot \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{n^2 \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right) \right) \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now we estimate the summation in set B . Note that for any positive integer α , the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha}}}$ is convergent, so from (2) and the definition of B we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in B} SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ SL(n)=p, p \leq \sqrt{n}}} p + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ SL(n)=p^\alpha, \alpha > 1}} p^\alpha \\ &\ll \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p|n, p \leq \sqrt{n}}} p + \sum_{2 \leq \alpha \leq \ln x} \sum_{p \leq x} \sum_{np^\alpha \leq x} p^\alpha \\ &\ll \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{p \leq \min\{n, \frac{x}{n}\}} p + \sum_{2 \leq \alpha \leq \ln x} \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{p \leq (\frac{x}{n})^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} p^\alpha \\ &\ll \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} + \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} \cdot \ln x \ll x^{\frac{3}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Combining (3), (6) and (7) we may immediately deduce that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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